

Retinal Image Registration and Mosaicking System for Comprehensive Wide-Field Visualization

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Abstract

Retinal imaging plays a crucial role in the diagnosis and monitoring of many ocular and systemic diseases, offering a non-invasive approach to analyse the retinal surface. Despite its multiple applications, the limited field-of-view in retinal images presents a major challenge for the comprehensive assessment of the retinal surface. To address this limitation, we propose a novel retinal image registration and mosaicking system that enables the creation of seamless wide-field retinal views. The system consists of a deep learning feature-based registration pipeline, including a novel two-stage RANSAC-based outlier rejection strategy and a robust deformable transformation model. Our outlier rejection strategy effectively captures global and local deformations, reducing the dominance of densely matched regions which may not fully characterize the entire image, resulting in a more reliable and evenly distributed inlier set. The final deformable transformation is achieved by applying an Approximate Thin-Plate Spline (ATPS) interpolation model, which accounts for potential keypoint localization errors, ensuring a precise and flexible alignment. Finally, we our α -blending method stitches together the images aligned to a common reference, creating smooth and seamless retinal mosaics. Evaluation on the reference FIRE dataset demonstrated that our retinal registration method outperformed all previous state-of-the-art methods. We additionally validated its robustness across other datasets, and tested the effectiveness of our blending method. The results demonstrated the superior performance of our system, and its consistency generating seamless wide-field retinal visualizations, ultimately enhancing diagnostic accuracy and treatment planning.

Keywords: Retinal image registration, Image Mosaicking, Feature-based Registration, Thin-Plate Spline interpolation, Deep Learning, Medical imaging

1 Introduction

Retinal images are essential in diagnosing and monitoring eye diseases such as diabetic retinopathy, glaucoma, or age-related macular degeneration, conditions that are the leading causes of vision loss globally [1]. Ocular pathologies can be asymptomatic for many years, thus early detection and accurate treatment are vital for preventing vision loss and maintaining patients' quality of life. Moreover, systemic diseases with strong vasculopathy, like hypertension or diabetes, can also be diagnosed and monitored through the analysis of the retinal vascularity [9]. Therefore, retinal imaging has become an indispensable tool in modern clinical practice, as it provides in vivo information of the retina and the vasculature through a non-invasive approach.

There are several imaging modalities designed to capture retinal images in a non-invasive manner, including Color Fundus (CF) imaging, Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT), and Fundus Angiography. Specifically, CF imaging holds particular significance due to its widespread use in clinical practice, accessibility, and cost-effectiveness [19]. However, most studies of retinal findings are limited by the field-of-view of the imaging modality [12].

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To address this limitation, retinal image registration and mosaicking techniques can be used together to create wide-field retinal views. Image registration is a fundamental task in image mosaicking, consisting of the alignment of two or more images taken from different perspectives, at different acquisition times, or with different acquisition devices [11]. The goal of image registration is to find a transformation that maps one image (the reference image) to another image (the target image), so that they are geometrically aligned. Beyond mosaicking, image registration plays a crucial role in medical imaging, due to its multiple applications in clinical practice [29]. Accurate alignment, not only supports the simultaneous analysis of multiple images helping clinicians draw more informed conclusions, but is also an important component for longitudinal studies, disease monitoring, and numerous computer-assisted diagnosis and treatment systems [18][32]. Once images are registered, mosaicking techniques can be used to stitch together the aligned images, creating a single comprehensive wide-field view [16]. In the context of retinal imaging, this wider view enables clinicians to detect and monitor changes across the retinal surface more accurately. Enhancing the registration and mosaicking accuracy can significantly benefit the clinical practice. By improving these techniques, clinicians can achieve faster and more reliable diagnoses, reducing diagnostic delays and increasing accuracy [13].

Image registration techniques can be classified into two main categories based on their methodologies: classical methods and deep learning based methods. Classical methods are widely used, however they rely on pre-processing and feature engineering, which can limit their adaptability. Deep learning methods overcome these limitations by learning directly from raw data to the desired output, enabling greater flexibility and robustness. This is particularly valuable in retinal image registration, where variability due to diseases, imaging devices, and capture conditions represent significant challenges [22].

Additionally, considering the type of information that is used for the alignment, any image registration technique can also be classified into three main groups: Intensity-Based Registration (IBR), Direct Parameter Regression (DPR), and Feature-Based Registration (FBR) [23]. IBR methods rely on optimizing a similarity metric to align images iteratively. DPR methods use neural networks to predict deformation fields or transformation matrices directly from the input images. Finally, FBR methods focus on identifying and matching distinctive keypoints in both images of a pair, such as blood vessel bifurcations or the optic disc. These keypoints are then used to infer the transformation between the images.

In the specific domain of retinal image registration, particularly for color fundus images, there are several challenges, such as large displacements and low degree of overlap between images, irregularities or artifacts like halos and blurriness, and small and scattered features like blood vessel bifurcations and crossovers that can be useful for registration. These factors limit the applicability of IBR methods due to the difficulty in defining robust similarity metrics, as well as the applicability of deformable DPR methods due to the risk of overfitting the transformation since retinal transformations are predominantly rigid. As a result, the specific characteristics of retinal images make the field predominantly reliant on FBR methods [25][21]. However, current FBR approaches also present important limitations: they often suffer from uneven keypoint distributions, sensitivity to outliers, and difficulty handling local deformations, which are common challenges when aligning eye fundus images.

To overcome these limitations, we propose a novel retinal image registration and mosaicking system that incorporates a deep learning FBR registration method specifically designed to enhance correspondence distribution, improve robustness against outliers, and accurately capture local deformations. Our system provides wide-field comprehensive views of the retinal surface, ultimately supporting more accurate diagnoses and effective treatment planning. For image registration, the proposed methodology integrates deep learning for feature detection and description, an outlier rejection strategy for locally refining correspondences, and a deformable transformation model. The main contributions of this methodology are our two-stage RANSAC-based outlier rejection strategy, and the use of a robust deformable transformation estimation model. The proposed outlier rejection approach effectively refines the set of correspondences by capturing both global and local deformations, ensuring a more accurate representation of the image pair. The key advantage to this method is not assuming a uniform transformation between image pairs, which reduces the influence of densely matched regions, resulting in a more reliable and evenly distributed set of inliers. Subsequently, the final robust deformable transformation is achieved by applying a regularized Thin-Plate Spline (TPS) interpolation. This regularized model accounts for potential keypoint localization errors, ensuring a more precise alignment between images. Lastly, for image mosaicking, we introduce our α -blending method that leverages the registration framework to seamlessly stitch together the images that have been aligned to a common reference image, creating accurate and smooth retinal mosaics. Finally, to validate our complete system, we conducted experiments with four different public datasets of retinal images. First, we evaluated our proposed registration method on the reference FIRE dataset [7], demonstrating its superior performance over state-of-the-art methods. Additionally, we assessed the general-

ization capability of our registration method across different datasets reflecting the variability encountered in clinical scenarios, and assessed the performance of our α -blending method for retinal image mosaicking. The results highlight the robustness of our approach and its ability to adapt to different imaging conditions and modalities, consistently generating comprehensive wide-field retinal views.

2 Related work

The field of retinal image registration is currently moving away from a dominance of classical methods to a growing adoption of deep learning methods, driven by their adaptability and flexibility. To reflect this methodological evolution, registration performance for color fundus (CF) images is commonly benchmarked using the FIRE dataset as reference, offering a consistent basis for evaluating and comparing both classical and learning-based methods.

Among classical methods, VOTUS [17] and REMPE [8] stand out. Specifically, VOTUS is the best-performing classical method on the FIRE dataset, and was not until recently that deep learning-based methods surpassed it in terms of performance. VOTUS registers images by constructing graphs of the arterio-venous tree. These graphs are matched using the Vessel Optimal Transform algorithm, which relies on classical image features, and the transformation matrix is computed using DeSAC (Deterministic Sample and Consensus). REMPE, on the other hand, identifies discrete keypoints using SIFT and blood vessel bifurcations. It computes the optimal transformation through RANSAC [6] and Particle Swarm Optimization, according to an eye-specific model specially designed for fundus images.

Recently, the emerging deep learning approaches have focused on improving the features description. SuperRetina [15] adapted SuperPoint [4] method to CF images, for jointly training a detector and descriptor using vessel keypoints and a triplet loss for descriptor learning. However, SuperRetina relies on extensive preprocessing, including extracting the green channel, normalizing it, applying CLAHE contrast enhancement [20], and performing gamma adjustment. It also uses a dual inference step, where matching is conducted with two methods to improve accuracy. These factors diminish some of the advantages of deep learning, as they increase the computational load and may require specific parameter tuning for preprocessing each dataset. These disadvantages were addressed by ConKeD [25], which introduced two independent supervised networks for detection and description. The descriptor network is trained with novel multi-positive and multi-negative losses, improving data efficiency over triplet-based approaches. ConKeD++ [24] further enhanced performance with a rank-wise contrastive loss, FastAP [3].

In parallel with these advances in feature description, recent efforts have shifted toward learning-based feature matching, aiming to directly establish reliable correspondences between images, addressing challenges such as complex transformations, occlusions, and appearance variations. GeoFormer [14] has demonstrated significant relevance as a deep learning detector-less method for CF image registration. Based on LoFTR’s [28] pipeline, GeoFormer leverages transformers to extract enhanced local features while performing feature matching. Additionally integrates RANSAC in the training process for further enhancing the local features.

Distinct from previous descriptor-focused and matcher-focused approaches, RetinaRegNet [27] introduced a novel paradigm to address key challenges in retinal image registration such as minimal overlap, large deformations, and variability in image quality, establishing as the most recent and top-performing method. RetinaRegNet is a zero-shot retinal image registration model that utilizes features from a stable diffusion model without requiring training on retinal images. It selects points using SIFT and random point sampling, matches them via a 2D correlation map, and eliminates outliers using an inverse consistency constraint combined with a RANSAC-based outlier detector. A two-stage approach is then employed to estimate complex transformations. This approach combines a homogeneous transformation for global alignment with a third-order polynomial for local refinement, establishing RetinaRegNet as the current state-of-the-art.

The main difference between our proposed retinal image registration method and previous deep learning approaches is that, while the latter have focus on improving feature description, our method focuses on refining the correspondences to obtain a more reliable set of inliers. The key contributions of our method are its refined RANSAC-based outlier detection strategy and the robust deformable transformation estimation. In this regard, our method shares some conceptual similarities with RetinaRegNet, but differs significantly in its approach. While RetinaRegNet applies RANSAC globally for outlier detection, our method applies RANSAC both globally and locally enabling effective detection of region-specific outliers, ensuring a more reliable and evenly distributed set of inliers. Another notable aspect of our outlier rejection approach is that it progressively increases the

Figure 1: Overview of the proposed retinal registration method

degrees of freedom of the transformation model, while simultaneously reducing the residual threshold, to further refine the inlier set. Additionally, unlike RetinaRegNet’s two-stage framework for global and local alignment, our method estimates the final transformation in a single step using a robust and smooth Thin-Plate Spline (TPS) interpolation, unifying global and local alignment for achieving precise, flexible and efficient registration.

3 Methods

In this section, we provide a detailed explanation of the methods employed and designed as part of our proposed framework for retinal image registration and mosaicking.

First, we propose a feature-based registration method for estimating the transformation between retinal image pairs. Figure 1 presents an overview of the proposed retinal registration framework, which consists of five steps: The first step is **keypoint extraction** (Section 3.1), where distinctive points are identified in both images of the pair. In the subsequent **feature extraction** step (Section 3.2), descriptors are computed for these keypoints, capturing unique characteristics. The descriptors are then compared in the **feature matching** step (Section 3.3) to establish a set of correspondences. Next, the **outlier rejection** step (Section 3.4) applies two methods, Incremental Degrees of Freedom (IDoF) and Local Affine, specifically designed to identify and exclude mismatches for obtaining a refined set. The **final transformation estimation** step (Section 3.5) computes a smooth Thin-Plate Spline interpolation based on the refined set of correspondences, producing a robust deformable transformation that aligns both images. Finally, a mosaicking method was designed (Section 3.6) to generate wide-field retinal views by seamlessly combining the aligned images.

3.1 Keypoint Extraction

The first step of the proposed methodology is the detection of the desired keypoints, which in this case are the pixels forming the vascular skeleton. For that purpose, we extract the vessel maps from both input images. Retinal blood vessels cover most of the retinal image and typically remain structurally and spatially stable even in a diseased eye. These characteristics make them reliable landmarks for registration, enabling an accurate alignment of images, and ensuring robust registration even in the presence of ocular pathologies.

To extract vessel maps, we employed the retinal vasculature segmentation network proposed by Hervella et al. in 2020 [10]. This model is trained using transfer learning with unlabeled pre-training data, addressing the need for large annotated datasets in deep learning. A U-Net model is pre-trained on a self-supervised multimodal reconstruction task using aligned retinography and fluorescein angiography image pairs. During pre-training, the network learns to reconstruct one modality from the other, capturing shared patterns between them. After pre-training, the network is fine-tuned to perform vessel segmentation directly on retinography images, leveraging the knowledge gained to reduce the need for annotated data and ensuring high accuracy.

Then, the obtained masks are skeletonized through morphological thinning using the algorithm proposed by Zhang and Suen, reducing them to single-pixel wide skeletons. Finally, the extracted skeleton pixel locations constitute the resulting keypoint set.

3.2 Feature Extraction

The second step involves generating descriptors for the detected keypoints. For this task, we used an unsupervised version of ConKeD++ [24], referred to as UnConKeD [26].

ConKeD [25] is a deep learning method to extract descriptors for retinal image registration. It employs a multi-positive multi-negative contrastive learning strategy to leverage information from training samples to learn high-quality descriptors. To achieve this, it is trained on multiviewed batches, containing both the original images and augmented versions generated through random affine transformations. ConKeD++ [24] further improves the method with the introduction of the FastAP loss [3], a rank-wise contrastive loss minimizing Average Precision (AP). UnConKeD [26] eliminates the need for labeled data by training on randomly sampled keypoints across the retinal surface, instead of relying on a supervised detection network to identify retinal keypoints for training. To ensure that both images in each pair have the same dimensions, they are rescaled to a fixed size while maintaining the aspect ratio. This is achieved resizing the smaller size of the image to fit the desired output size, and scaling the larger side proportionally. After rescaling, the images are centrally cropped to make both dimensions equal, resulting in images with same shape and aspect ratio. Due to UnConked’s resolution restrictions, input images are resized to 832×832 pixels.

Each preprocessed image is then passed through the UnConKeD network, which generates a dense descriptor block, representing the desired features across the entire image. Finally, the vessel skeleton mask for each image is reshaped to match the preprocessed image, and the descriptors corresponding to the keypoint locations are selected.

3.3 Feature Matching

The third step involves matching the descriptors obtained from the images in each registration pair. This process is carried out using a brute-force matching approach, where the distance between descriptors is measured by means of cosine similarity.

The process is as follows: For each descriptor in the reference image, its closest match in the set of descriptors of target image is found. Then, the match is established as valid only if they are the closest to each other in their respective sets. This mutual criterion ensures the reliability of the matches, which are then used in the subsequent steps of the registration process.

Matching is performed at the same resolution as the feature extraction, and the matched keypoints are then upsampled to the original image resolution. This upscaling ensures that the images can be aligned in their original dimensions, which is essential for a fair comparison among methods.

3.4 Outlier Rejection

This step focuses on identifying a subset of inliers that represent the most consistent and reliable matches from the previous step, while rejecting the outliers. This phase is crucial for ensuring accurate alignment when estimating the final transformation. The method consists on combining two techniques called **Incremental Degrees of Freedom** and **Local Affine**, which are explained below.

3.4.1 Incremental Degrees of Freedom (IDoF)

This method aims to robustly detect and exclude outliers using the well-established RANSAC (Random Sample Consensus) algorithm to fit a transformation model. It applies RANSAC in two stages, progressively increasing the complexity of the transformation model while simultaneously reducing the residual threshold, in order to achieve both robustness against noise and precision.

In the first stage, RANSAC is applied to fit a Euclidean transformation, which models translation and rotation. This model has fewer degrees of freedom, making it less prone to overfitting. A higher error threshold is used in this step to capture a broad set of potential inliers, ensuring that the algorithm focuses on identifying a core subset of matches that provide a stable foundation.

In the second stage, RANSAC is applied to the detected inliers to fit an Affine transformation, which introduces additional degrees of freedom, enabling to account for scaling, shearing, rotation and translation. This allows to capture subtle variations in the data that the Euclidean model could not account for. A smaller threshold is used at this stage, imposing stricter alignment criteria to further refine the inlier set, ensuring more precise and reliable correspondences.

Figure 2: Overview of the proposed Local Affine method

This approach of progressive increasing the degrees of freedom while reducing the residual threshold enables to exclude gross outliers early on while refining the inlier set.

3.4.2 Local Affine

This method is designed to locally detect and exclude outlier matches, obtaining an accurate representation of different regions of the image pair. As shown in Figure 1, it is applied as the second stage of the IDoF method within our registration framework.

Figure 2 illustrates how the Local Affine method works. The process begins by taking as input the set of inliers obtained from the first stage of the IDoF method. Next, the target image is divided into 9 equally sized quadrants. For each quadrant, RANSAC with an Affine transformation is applied to the matches whose target coordinates fall within the quadrant (these matches may correspond to any point in the reference image). Finally, the inliers obtained for each quadrant are combined to form the final set of inliers.

The key to this method lies in its ability to capture region-specific deformations without assuming a uniform transformation across the entire image. This strategy reduces the influence of areas with a higher density of matches, which may not accurately represent the entire image pair. This offers a flexible and robust solution, especially for pairs with regions containing significant anatomical changes.

3.5 Final Transformation estimation

This step involves estimating the final transformation $f(x, y)$ that can be applied to every pixel in the target image to generate an image that is aligned to the reference image.

For this purpose, the **Approximate Thin-plate spline transformation (ATPS)** interpolation is performed using the inliers obtained from the previous step. Subsequently, to wrap the target image, the transformation is applied to the coordinates of the target image, and the pixels values for the transformed coordinates are obtained by interpolation.

3.5.1 Thin-plate spline transformation (TPS)

TPS interpolation is a mathematical method used to smoothly transform one set of points into another. It is based on the idea of bending a thin, flexible plate that is constrained at specific points. TPS can be used for

estimating the transformation for point-based registration in 2-D images, given a target image T , a reference image R , and a set of n corresponding points:

$$P_0 : \{(\mathbf{p}_i, \mathbf{q}_i) \mid \mathbf{p}_i \in T, \mathbf{q}_i \in R, i = 1, \dots, n\}.$$

The goal is to find a transformation $f(x, y)$ that maps the input coordinates of the target image to its corresponding position in the the reference image, according to the set corresponding points. The transformation is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} f(x, y) &= \Phi_s(x, y) + R_s(x, y) \\ &= (a_1 + a_x x + a_y y) + \sum_{i=1}^n \omega_i U(r_i) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $U(r_i) = r_i^2 \log r_i^2$ is the radial basis function, and $r_i = \|(x, y) - \mathbf{p}_i\|$ is the Euclidean distance between (x, y) and control point \mathbf{p}_i . The transformation consists of two parts:

- The affine part $\Phi_s(x, y)$: a sum of polynomials with coefficients $\mathbf{a} = (a_1, a_x, a_y)$ that determining translation, scaling, and rotation, for each dimension.
- The elastic part $R_s(x, y)$: a sum of radial basis functions with coefficients $\boldsymbol{\omega} = (\omega_1, \omega_2, \dots, \omega_n)$, that models the bending energy of the thin plate.

The weights $\mathbf{a} = (a_1, a_x, a_y)$ and $\boldsymbol{\omega} = (\omega_1, \omega_2, \dots, \omega_n)$ are determined by solving a system of equations that ensures that the transformation passes through all the control points, while minimizing the bending energy $E_{TPS}(f)$:

$$E_{TPS}(f) = \iint \left| \frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial x^2} \right|^2 + \left| \frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial x \partial y} \right|^2 + \left| \frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial y^2} \right|^2 dx dy \quad (2)$$

Finally, the system of equations to be solved in order to obtain the TPS coefficients is:

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{K}\boldsymbol{\omega} + \mathbf{P}\mathbf{a} &= \mathbf{v} \\ \mathbf{P}^T\boldsymbol{\omega} &= \mathbf{O} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where:

- \mathbf{K} is a matrix of the radial basis function values between control points, where K_{ij} is $U(\|\mathbf{p}_j - \mathbf{p}_i\|)$
- \mathbf{w} are the weights for the non-linear term
- \mathbf{P} is a matrix containing the control points, where the i th row of \mathbf{P} is $(1, p_{i_x}, p_{i_y})$
- \mathbf{a} are the affine parameters
- \mathbf{v} are the reference points
- \mathbf{O} is a 3x3 matrix of zeros

Note that the second equation, $\mathbf{P}^T\boldsymbol{\omega} = \mathbf{O}$, represents the boundary conditions and ensures that the elastic part of the transformation is zero at infinity.

3.5.2 Approximate TPS (ATPS)

The standard TPS interpolation described above, requires solving a system of equations that ensures target points are mapped exactly to their corresponding reference points. This process assumes that landmark positions are perfectly accurate. However, in real application the locations of landmarks are prone to errors. To address this the interpolation criterion needs to be weakened. This can be achieved by introducing an approximation criterion combined with the bending energy function, which weakens interpolation condition by incorporating a quadratic approximation term. This results in the following objective function:

$$J_\lambda(f) = \sum_{i=1}^n |\mathbf{q}_i - f(\mathbf{p}_i)|^2 + \lambda E_{\text{TPS}}(f) \quad (4)$$

The first term of the approximation criterion, Eq. 4, measures the sum of the squared Euclidean distances between the transformed target landmarks $f(\mathbf{p}_i)$ and the reference landmarks \mathbf{q}_i , representing alignment errors. This term allows the TPS interpolation to account for imprecise alignment.

The second term in Eq. 4 measures the smoothness of the resulting transformation. A regularization parameter, λ ($\lambda > 0$), is introduced to control the trade-off between alignment accuracy (first term) and transformation smoothness (second term). When λ is small prioritizes closer alignment, ensuring that transformed landmarks closely match the reference landmarks, but at the cost of a less smooth transformation. When λ is large, favors smoother transformations, by allowing greater deviations between transformed and reference landmarks, reducing sensitivity to individual landmarks.

The solutions to the ATPS interpolation is similar to standard TPS, with the difference of including the regularization term $\lambda \mathbf{I}$ in the diagonal of the matrix \mathbf{K} of the first equation:

$$\begin{cases} (\mathbf{K} + \lambda \mathbf{I}) \boldsymbol{\omega} + \mathbf{P} \mathbf{a} & = \mathbf{v} \\ \mathbf{P}^T \boldsymbol{\omega} & = \mathbf{O} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{I} is the identity matrix. This integrates the regularization term directly into the system, enabling the approximation and smoothing effects.

3.6 Mosaicking (α -blending)

Finally, we developed the α -blending method to perform image mosaicking. The method aims to generate mosaics by combining multiple images that have been aligned to a common reference image. The approach is specifically designed to achieve smooth transitions in areas where the images overlap, minimizing any abrupt changes in intensity, and resulting in a visually cohesive final mosaic. The process consists of applying five steps to the all images that have been aligned to a shared reference image:

Step 1: Determining the Mosaic Size. The first step is to define the overall dimensions of the mosaic, ensuring that all the transformed images fit within the defined space.

We start by identifying the corner coordinates of the reference image, which are then transformed using the estimated transformations for each reference-target pair. The width of the mosaic is obtained by subtracting the minimum x-coordinate of the transformed corners from the maximum x-coordinate, representing the total width required to fit all the transformed images. The same calculation is done for the y-coordinates to determine the height of the mosaic.

Step 2: Computing a translation matrix. The second step involves obtaining a translation matrix to ensure that the reference image is centered within the mosaic, taking into account all the transformed positions of its corners.

The translation along the x-direction is given by $-\text{offset}_x$, and along the y-direction by $-\text{offset}_y$. The value of offset_x is computed by subtracting the width of the reference image from the width of the mosaic, and then adding the smallest x-coordinate of the transformed corners. Similarly, offset_y is obtained using the corresponding heights and the smallest y-coordinate of the transformed corners.

Step 3: Processing the Reference Image. Involves performing the computations for the reference image blending. It involves translating the reference image, defining the region of interest (ROI), and generating a weight map to ensure smooth integration with the target images.

The reference image is aligned to the mosaic using the translation matrix. Then, a binary mask defining the ROI, which is circular area containing the retina, is obtained. The mask is created by identifying non-black pixels within the image. To prevent edge artifacts when blending, the mask boundaries are slightly eroded. Finally, the center (x_c, y_c) and the radius r of the retina are measured in the resulting area.

Subsequently, a weight map is created to guide the blending process. This map assigns higher weights to pixels near the center of the retina, and lower weights to those farther away. The weight for each pixel (x, y) is calculated based on its Euclidean distance to the center (x_c, y_c) . A Gaussian function is applied to the distances to ensure smooth transitions from the center to the edges, where the smoothing parameter σ is determined by

$r/2.5$. To ensure that only the region of the retina contributes to the blending, the final weight map for the reference image, $w_{\text{ref}}(x, y)$, is restricted to the ROI mask. Finally, the weight map is normalized so that the weights range between 0 and 1, with the center of the retina receiving a weight of 1, while the weights decrease gradually toward the edges, reaching 0 outside the radius of the retina.

Step 4: Processing the Target Images. Involves calculating the target images’ blending maps.

For each target image, both the translation matrix and its corresponding estimated transformation aligning it to the reference image are applied. Finally, the ROI mask and weight map w_{target_i} are obtained following the procedure described in Step 3.

Step 5: Constructing the Final Mosaic. The final mosaic is created by blending all the aligned images, reference and targets, using their respective weight maps, $w_{\text{ref}}(x, y)$ and $w_{\text{target}_i}(x, y)$.

Each aligned image $I_i(x, y)$ is multiplied by its corresponding weight map, $w_i(x, y)$. The results for all images are summed together and then divided by the total weight at each pixel, which is the sum of all weight maps at that location. Mathematically, the intensity of a pixel in the mosaic at coordinates (x, y) is given by:

$$\text{mosaic}(x, y) = \frac{\sum_i I_i(x, y) \cdot w_i(x, y)}{\sum_i w_i(x, y)} \quad (6)$$

In this formulation, each transformed image contributes to the mosaic according to its respective weight map. This ensures that areas where multiple images overlap are blended proportionally to their weights. The final mosaic results in a smooth and seamless representation of the combined images.

4 Materials

4.1 Datasets

This section presents the four retinal datasets used in this study, each serving specific purposes. **FIRE** [7] dataset served as reference for evaluating our registration method (Section 5.1), and benchmarking it against state-of-the-art methods for retinal registration (Section 5.2). **FIMD** [30], **FLoRI21** [5], and **LDRScreening** [2] were employed to assess our registration method robustness and generalization ability (Section 5.3). Moreover, FLoRI21 and LDRScreening provided the foundation to assess our mosaicking method. Detailed descriptions of each dataset are provided below.

Fundus Image Registration dataset (FIRE)

FIRE [7] is a dataset designed to validate and benchmark image registration methods in retinal imaging. It comprises retinal image pairs annotated with corresponding image points, and a protocol to evaluate registration accuracy. The dataset consists of 134 retinal fundus image pairs, with a resolution of 2912×2912 pixels. These pairs are categorized into three groups based on their the degree of spatial overlap and the presence or absence of anatomical differences. Category *S* contains 71 image pairs with a large spatial overlap (>75%) and no visual anatomical differences. Category *P* contains 49 image pairs with a smaller overlap (< 75%). Category *A* contains 14 image pairs with a large overlap (> 75%), that were acquired at different examinations, and present visual anatomical changes due to the progression or remission of retinopathy. This changes may appear in the form of increased vessel tortuosity, micro-aneurysms, cotton-wool, spots, and other features associated with retinal disease. Additionally, all three categories may feature eye shape deformations caused by myopia, hypermetropia, and similar conditions.

Each image pair is annotated with 10 corresponding points strategically located on blood vessels and crossings that are widely distributed across the image. This ensures broad coverage of the overlapping regions, enabling accurate evaluation of registration performance. These annotations make the FIRE dataset a comprehensive resource for evaluating the robustness of image registration methods under a variety of conditions that may be present in clinical cases.

Fundus Image Myopia Development dataset (FIMD)

The FIMD dataset [30] is also designed for validation of image registration techniques, particularly in the context of longitudinal studies of myopia progression. It contains 70 retinal fundus image pairs of varying

sizes, characterized by a large overlap area, and evidence of myopia development, without the presence of other retinopathies. The time interval between the images in each pair range from one to five years, and the images were acquired with different fundus cameras, leading to different image resolutions, brightness, contrast and field of view in between pairs. This additional complexity makes this dataset a valuable resource for testing the robustness of image registration algorithms under diverse imaging conditions.

Following the FIRE annotation method, FIMD pairs are labeled with 12 widely and uniformly distributed control points, mainly located at blood vessels bifurcation and crossing, providing reliable landmarks for accurate registration.

Fluorescein Angiography Longitudinal Retinal Image Registration Dataset (FLoRI21)

FLoRI21 [5] is a collection of ultra-widefield fluorescein angiography images designed for retinal image registration validation. The dataset contains 15 images with a resolution of 3900×3072 pixels. Images were captured from five different subjects, each subject contributing from 2 to 4 images, taken approximately 24 weeks apart.

For each subject there is a montage image that serves as the common reference image for registration, leading to a total of 15 reference-target image pairs. All pairs are annotated with control points that were strategically selected to ensure comprehensive coverage across the overlapping regions between the reference and target images.

Longitudinal diabetic retinopathy screening dataset (LDRScreening)

LDRScreening [2] is a dataset designed for retinal image registration and mosaicking research. The dataset comprises a total of 1120 retinal fundus images collected from 70 patients with diabetes during their annual retinal examinations. Each subject contributed 16 images, captured as follows: four distinct views per eye (macula-centered, optic nerve-centered, superior, and temporal regions of the retina), taken from both eyes, and across two separate visits. All images have a resolution of 2000×1312 pixels.

In addition to the original retinal fundus images, the dataset includes a normalized version of these images that is obtained by applying a higher-order normalized convolution for enhanced visibility of retinal features. Lastly, it also contains intra-visit and inter-visit mosaic movies generated using two different image registration methods.

In this study, we use the smaller version of the dataset called LDRScreening small, which consists of a subset of four eyes (32 images in total).

4.2 Evaluation

This section outlines the methods employed to evaluate the performance of our registration framework. We use two evaluation methodologies, direct and surrogate evaluation, to assess performance across the four datasets described in Section 4.1. Direct evaluation provides precise numerical assessments for datasets that include ground truth in the form of control points, while surrogate evaluation is designed to assess registration in datasets without control points.

4.2.1 Direct evaluation

We employed the FIRE evaluation method to quantitatively assess the accuracy of the estimated transformations. This method determines registration error by measuring the misalignment between image pairs after applying the estimated transformation to the target image.

The error is computed using control points as the ground truth. For each image pair, takes the coordinates of control points in the reference image and maps them to the target image using the estimated transformation. The registration error is computed as the mean euclidean distance between the original control point coordinates in the target image and the estimated coordinates. A registration is considered successful if the error falls below a specified threshold.

To assess the overall performance, the percentage of successfully registered image pairs is plotted against a varying error threshold. The Area Under the Curve (AUC) is derived from the plot, calculated within a defined range of 0-100% success ratio and 0-25 pixels of registration error. The AUC value represents the final registration score, providing a robust metric for evaluating the effectiveness of registration methods.

4.2.2 Surrogate evaluation based on similarity

This evaluation was designed for datasets that lack control points, which are necessary for performing direct quantitative evaluation, as in the case of the LDRScreening dataset.

The surrogate evaluation is performed using the normalized images from the LDRScreening dataset. For each reference-target image pair, the binary retinal segmentation masks of both images is determined to define the ROI, which represents the circular area containing the retina. This masks are created by identifying non-black pixels within each image, and are then employed to identify the overlapping region between the reference and the target image. To prevent edge artifacts from interfering with the evaluation, the boundaries of the overlap mask are slightly eroded. The overlap mask is then applied to both the reference image and the transformed target image and three evaluation metrics are measured over them:

- **Mean Sum of Absolute Difference (MSAD)**: obtained by computing the absolute difference within the overlap area, adding up all the obtained pixels, and dividing by the total number of pixels in the overlap area.
- **Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM)** [31]: measures the similarity of two images based on three comparison measurements: luminance (l), contrast (c) and structure (s). Its value ranges from -1 to 1, where 1 indicates perfect similarity between the images and -1 indicates complete dissimilarity.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{SSIM}(x, y) &= l(x, y) \cdot c(x, y) \cdot s(x, y) \\ &= \frac{(2\mu_x\mu_y + C_1) + (2\sigma_{xy} + C_2)}{(\mu_x^2 + \mu_y^2 + C_1)(\sigma_x^2 + \sigma_y^2 + C_2)} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where μ_x and μ_y represent the mean pixel values of images x and y , σ_x^2 and σ_y^2 are the variances, and σ_{xy} is the covariance between the images. The local statistics for each pixel are computed using a Gaussian window with $\sigma = 1.5$. The constant values $C_1 = (k_1L)^2$ and $C_2 = (k_2L)^2$ are used to avoid instability when the denominator terms are close to zero, where L is the dynamic range of pixel values (e.g., 255), and k_1, k_2 are small constants, $k_1 = 0.01$ and $k_2 = 0.03$ by default.

- **Peak signal-to-noise ratio (PSNR)**: measures the similarity between two images expressed as a logarithmic quantity using the decibel scale. The higher the PSNR, the more similar the images are, while lower PSNR values mean more significant differences between the images.

$$\text{PSNR}(x, y) = 20 \log \frac{MAX_I}{\sqrt{MSE}} \quad (8)$$

where MAX_I is the maximum valid value for a pixel in the image, and MSE is the Mean Squared Error:

$$\text{MSE} = \frac{1}{mn} \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n (x_{ij} - y_{ij})^2 \quad (9)$$

where m is the number of rows and n the columns.

5 Experiments

This section provides a detailed overview of the experiments conducted to evaluate the performance and robustness of our proposed method for retinal image registration and mosaicking.

5.1 Ablation Study

We performed an ablation study to assess the impact of the different steps and techniques integrated into our methodology for retinal image registration.

We designed five configurations in which we progressively added the most novel components of our method, described in Section 3. All five configurations share the first three steps of the pipeline, which involve: extracting keypoints from the input image pairs, computing feature descriptors for the obtained points, and performing feature matching with the resulting descriptors of both images (see Sections 3.1, 3.2 and 3.3). The configurations differ in the methods used for outlier rejection and transformation estimation, which are outlined in the following:

- **Baseline:** This serves as the baseline configuration, where both outlier rejection and transformation estimation are performed together in a single RANSAC step. The RANSAC method with an Affine transformation is used for this process.
- **RANSAC Affine + TPS:** In this second configuration we refined the baseline by using the RANSAC with an Affine transformation step exclusively for outlier detection, and introducing the Thin-Plate Spline (TPS) interpolation model (Section 3.5.1) to estimate the final transformation. This allows us to use a more flexible model that better adapts to the data, while still being robust, since the TPS treats all the matches as inliers.
- **IDoF + TPS:** In this configuration, we further improved the outlier rejection step by replacing the previous method with our Incremental Degrees of Freedom (IDoF) method (Section 3.4.1). This approach aims to provide a more accurate and reliable set of inliers, improving the robustness of the transformation estimation.
- **IDoF + Local Affine + TPS:** Building on the last one, we introduce additional refinement to outlier rejection by incorporating our Local Affine method (Section 3.4.2) into the second step of the IDoF method. This aims to improve the inlier set by capturing fine-grained and region-specific variations, instead of assuming a uniform Affine transformation across the entire image.
- **IDoF + Local Affine + ATPS:** The final configuration consists on further refining the transformation estimation step by replacing the TPS interpolation with a regularized and smoother version, the Approximate Thin-Plate Spline (ATPS). As detailed in Section 3.5.2, the ATPS model accounts for possible imprecisely localized matches, that might be present even after the outlier rejection step, ensuring a more accurate final transformation.

The experiments were carried out using all image pairs from the FIRE dataset, and the results were compared using the direct evaluation described in Section 4.2.1. Additionally, we tested several parameter values to determine the optimal settings for each configuration:

- Residual threshold for RANSAC with an Euclidean transformation (rE): 15, 25, and 30
- Residual threshold for RANSAC with an Affine transformation (rA): 1, 1.5, 2.5, 5, and 10. This also applies when used within the IDoF and Local Affine methods.
- ATPS regularization parameter (λ): 2.5×10^k , $k = 3, \dots, 6$.

5.2 Comparison with State of the Art

This experiment evaluates our retinal image registration method against other state-of-the-art approaches on the reference FIRE dataset. The aim of the experiment is to assess performance of our method in relation to established techniques within the same domain and on the same dataset, including both classical and deep learning-based methods.

We compared the results of our IDoF + Local Affine + ATPS method (Section 5.1) with those reported on the FIRE dataset by **VOTUS** [17], **REMPE** [8], **SuperRetina** [15], **ConKeD** [25], **ConKeD++** [24], **GeoFormer** [14], and **RetinaRegNet** [27] (described in Section 2).

5.3 Generalization to other datasets and mosaicking

We designed this experiment to evaluate the generalization capability of our proposed registration method across different datasets. Moreover, we assessed the performance of our registration method when integrated with our blending method as part of the proposed retinal image mosaicking system.

The experiment involves applying our IDoF + Local Affine + ATPS registration method to image pairs from FIMD, FLoRI21, and LDRScreening datasets (see Section 4.1), and additionally our α -blending method to the images from the FLoRI21 and LDRScreening. These datasets, acquired using different imaging protocols and scanners, present unique characteristics and challenges, reflecting the variability encountered in clinical scenarios and making them ideal for evaluating the robustness of our methodology. Below, we detail the procedure and the adjustments made for each dataset:

Figure 3: Example of the modality adaptation preprocessing for a FLoRI21 image

- **FIMD**: In this dataset, due to the different acquisition processes, the images of each pair have different sizes. To account for this, we replaced the Euclidean transformation in the outlier rejection step (Section 3.4) with a Similarity transformation, which extends the transformation with a scale factor.

To evaluate FIMD registration results, direct evaluation was performed on the transformations estimated for all the image pairs, following the procedure detailed in Section 4.2.1.

- **FLoRI21**: given that this dataset consists of fluorescein angiography images, we introduced a preprocessing step that modifies the image appearance to resemble color fundus images, thus ensuring compatibility with the pre-trained vessel extraction and descriptor networks (Sections 3.1 and 3.2).

Preprocessing consists of performing histogram matching, taking as reference the average histogram of the FIRE images for each channel. Figure 3 shows an example of this approach. The preprocessing workflow is as follows:

1. Each fluorescein angiography image is inverted (see Figure 3b), as vessels appear light on a dark background in these images, unlike the dark-on-light representation in color fundus images. To ensure consistent behaviour, the date stamps in the bottom-left corner are filled with white pixels across all images
2. Then, a center crop of the inverted image (scaled by a factor of 1.5 of the image size) is taken to keep the representation close to the optic disk and exclude furthest areas that might introduce artifacts.
3. Histogram matching is performed using the center crop histogram and reference histograms from the FIRE dataset, with values below 0.11 clipped to prevent vessel obscuration near the optic disc that can lead to inaccuracies in segmentation. Each channel of the inverted image is adjusted to match the average cumulative distribution function of the reference histograms (see Figure 3c).

The FLoRI21 dataset does not specify which image is used as reference for constructing the mosaics of each subject. To address this, we established a simple heuristic: the image with the highest number of vessel pixels in its mask is chosen as the reference, as it likely overlaps most with the others. This approach avoids the computational cost of estimating transformations for all image pairs to determine which one has the largest overlap with the others.

After preprocessing the images and selecting the reference for each subject, our registration method is applied to align the remaining images of the subject to the reference. Finally, our α -blending method (Section 3.6) is applied to obtain a wide-field retinal mosaic for each subject.

To evaluate the registration results, direct evaluation was performed on the estimated transformations for all the reference-target pairs, as described in Section 4.2.1. Since control points are provided in the final montage, those corresponding to the same coordinates in the reference montage were used for each reference-target pair. The image *Raw_FA_2_Subject.2.tif* was excluded from the evaluation due to inconsistencies in its control points, which differed from the other images for the same subject.

- **LDRScreening**: this dataset did not require any specific modifications to our proposed method. For the experiment, we used the images collected for each eye across both clinical visits. As with FLoRI21, the dataset lacks reference image details for mosaics, so the same heuristic was applied to select the reference

	RANSAC Affine	IDoF	Local Affine	TPS	ATPS	AUC (a)	AUC (p)	AUC (s)	AUC (all)
Configuration 1	✓					0.7828	0.1134	0.9464	0.6247
Configuration 2	✓			✓		0.6885	0.0465	0.8946	0.5629
Configuration 3		✓		✓		0.7514	0.1053	0.8873	0.5871
Configuration 4		✓	✓	✓		0.7457	0.7787	0.8949	0.8367
Configuration 5		✓	✓		✓	0.8314	0.8718	0.9758	0.9227

Table 1: Evaluation results for the Ablation Study on FIRE dataset

	rE	rA	λ
Configuration 1		10.0	
Configuration 2		1.0	
Configuration 3	15.0	1.5	
Configuration 4	25.0	1.0	
Configuration 5	25.0	5.0	2.5×10^5

Table 2: Parameter settings for the Ablation Study configurations

image for each visit. Our registration method was then applied to align the remaining images from the same visit to the reference to the reference. Finally, our α -blending was applied to create a wide-field retinal mosaic for each visit.

Surrogate evaluation was conducted to assess the registration results for each reference-target image pair, following the procedure described in Section 4.2.2.

6 Results and Discussion

This section presents the results of the experiments described in the previous section, along with a thorough discussion of the findings and their implications.

6.1 Ablation Study

Table 1 presents the evaluation results for the ablation study described Section 5.1. The optimal parameter settings for each configuration is shown in Table 2. The results demonstrate a progressive improvement in registration performance across the FIRE dataset categories as more of the proposed components were integrated into our method.

Configuration 1 represents baseline configuration, where RANSAC with an Affine transformation is used for both outlier rejection and final transformation estimation. This configuration achieved an AUC of 0.7828 for category A, 0.1134 for category P, 0.9464 for category S, and 0.6247 overall. We can observe that P category presents the greatest challenge, with significantly lower performance compared to A and S.

Configuration 2 refined the baseline by using RANSAC with an Affine transformation exclusively for outlier rejection, and introducing the deformable Thin-Plate Spline (TPS) interpolation model for transformation estimation. However, the performance worsened across all categories, underscoring the limitations of relying on a single RANSAC step for outlier rejection when paired with a deformable model. The TPS model over-fits to all matching points, leading to excessively deformed and unstable transformations.

In **Configuration 3**, the Incremental Degrees of Freedom (IDoF) method was introduced for outlier rejection. The results reveal improvements over Configuration 2 in categories A and P, with AUC values of 0.7514 and 0.1053, respectively. However, the method is still not robust enough to improve the baseline results in any of the three categories.

Configuration 4 incorporated the Local Affine step, further refining outlier rejection process by capturing fine-grained, region-specific variations. This enhancement significantly improved the results across category P, where the AUC reached a value of 0.7787, yielding an overall AUC of 0.8367. This results significantly outperforms the baseline in both the P category and the overall performance. The improvement in category P

(a) Inliers using IDoF without Local Affine (Configuration 3) (b) Inliers using IDoF with Local Affine (Configuration 4)

Figure 4: Comparison of inliers obtained with IDoF method with and without the Local Affine

(a) Category A

(b) Category P

(c) Category S

Figure 5: Registration results of our proposed method for FIRE dataset

demonstrates that the Local Affine step effectively addressed the challenges posed in category P, where often most matches are concentrated in a specific region, typically around the optic disc. In this scenario, without the Local Affine step, RANSAC tends to fit transformations biased toward this overrepresented area, resulting in an inlier set that provides poor coverage of the overlapping region. However, the Local Affine method is able to capture localized variations in under-represented areas, ensuring a more even distribution of the final inlier matches across the overlapping region. This is illustrated in Figure 4, which compares for a P image pair the inliers obtained with and without the Local Affine step, demonstrating its impact on effectively increasing the inliers spatial distribution.

The final **Configuration 5** replaced TPS with the Approximate Thin-Plate Spline (ATPS), a regularized version that accounts for potential keypoint localization errors in the inlier set. This refinement led to the best performance across all categories, with an AUC of 0.8314 for category A, 0.8718 for category P, and 0.9758 for category S, resulting in an overall AUC of 0.9227. The improvements in category P underscore the ATPS model’s capacity to handle large displacement transformations with higher precision. The enhanced performance in category A and S highlights its capacity to mitigate the impact of mislocalized matches, ensuring more precise transformations.

The results demonstrate the improvements gained by progressively enhancing the pipeline with the proposed components. Configuration 5, with the inclusion of ATPS and a refined outlier rejection step, achieved state-of-the-art performance across all categories, effectively addressing the challenges of the FIRE dataset. These findings highlight reliability of our proposed method for retinal image registration in diverse clinical scenarios. Finally, Figure 5 illustrates the registration accuracy of our proposed method (Configuration 5) with an example from each category of the FIRE dataset.

6.2 Comparison with State of the Art

Table 3 shows the comparison on the reference FIRE dataset between our registration method and the state-of-the-art methods.

The results demonstrate that our model significantly outperformed all the previous methods in all categories of the FIRE dataset. The largest improvement is observed in category A, characterized by visual anatomical changes caused by retinopathy progression, where our method achieved an AUC of 0.831 outperforming

	<i>AUC</i> (a)	<i>AUC</i> (p)	<i>AUC</i> (s)	<i>AUC</i> (all)
VOTUS [17] (2019)	0.681	0.672	0.934	0.812
REMPE [8] (2020)	0.660	0.542	<u>0.958</u>	0.773
SuperRetina [15] (2022)	0.783	0.542	0.940	0.778
GeoFormer [14] (2023)	0.760	0.559	0.944	0.784
ConKeD [25] (2024)	0.749	0.489	0.945	0.758
ConKeD++ [24] (2024)	0.766	0.503	0.945	0.765
RetinaRegNet [27] (2025)	<u>0.805</u>	<u>0.856</u>	0.951	<u>0.901</u>
Ours	0.831	0.872	0.976	0.923

Table 3: Comparison with the State of the Art methods for retinal image registration on FIRE dataset

Dataset	AUC	Dataset	MSAD ↓	SSIM ↑	PSNR ↑
FIMD	0.8543	LDRScreening	7.6501	0.9558	35.5197
FLoRI21	0.4000 *				

(a) Direct evaluation results for FIMD and FLoRI21

(b) Surrogate evaluation results for LDRScreening

Table 4: Evaluation results for FIMD, FLoRI21 and LDRScreening datasets. * Indicates that the result was computed using one image less, as explained in the experimental details provided in Section 5.3

RetinaRegNet’s 0.805. In category S, our method obtained an AUC of 0.976, clearly surpassing the 0.958 achieved by REMPE [8]. Lastly, we can observe that until RetinaRegNet [27], category P has been particularly challenging due to the small overlaps between its pairs, implying large displacement transformations. Our method effectively addresses this issue achieving an AUC of 0.872, and further surpassing the 0.856 achieved by RetinaRegNet. The results highlight our method superior ability to obtain highly accurate alignments across the diverse categories underscoring its exceptional performance and reliability. These findings demonstrate its superiority in dealing with the challenges presented within the FIRE dataset, setting a new benchmark for future advancements in the field of retinal image registration.

6.3 Generalization to other datasets and mosaicking

Table 4 shows the evaluation results for FIMD, FLoRI21 and LDRScreening datasets, highlighting its performance across diverse imaging conditions and modalities:

For the FIMD dataset, our method achieved an AUC of 0.8543, demonstrating its robustness when applied to other datasets of color fundus images beyond FIRE. This strong performance underscores the method’s adaptability to the variability present in longitudinal studies. The FIMD dataset exemplifies these challenges by introducing anatomical changes from myopia progression, and variations in image resolution, brightness or contrast from the different acquisition devices. Despite these complexities, our method has proven highly effective, reinforcing its ability to generalize across different datasets and acquisition conditions.

On the other hand, our method achieved an AUC of 0.4000 in the alignment of FLoRI21 pairs. This results indicates lower performance compared to FIMD and FIRE datasets. This disparity can be attributed to the dataset’s distinct imaging modality. While preprocessing was performed to adapt the images, the vessel map extraction and feature description networks used in our method are trained for color fundus images. As a result, they are less effective when applied to the FLoRI21 data. The description step, in particular, is crucial for obtaining accurate matches, and its reduced effectiveness in this modality contributes significantly to the lower performance. One potential approach to improve the results on the FLoRI21 dataset would be to train these networks using fluorescein angiography images. By adapting the networks to this imaging modality, it would likely be possible to enhance their ability to extract meaningful features and establish accurate matches, therefore improving overall alignment performance.

The evaluation results for LDRScreening dataset, demonstrate once again the exceptional performance of our method when applied to a dataset of color fundus images. Our method achieved a SSIM of 0.9558, which is

Figure 6: Registration results of our proposed method for each dataset.

Figure 7: Examples of mosaics obtained for FLoRI21 using the proposed α -blending method

remarkably close to the theoretical maximum value of 1, which indicates perfect similarity between images. It is particularly impressive given that the overlap area in the aligned normalized image pairs may exhibit minor differences in luminance, contrast, and structural details.

Figure 6 presents registration examples obtained with our method for each of the three datasets, demonstrating highly accurate alignment in all cases. In particular, the accuracy achieved for the FIMD pair (Figure 6a) is noteworthy, given the challenging differences in image conditions between the two images.

In order to evaluate the mosaicking results and the effect of the blending method, Figures 7 and 8 show mosaics generated using our α -blending method, showing its effectiveness in creating seamless wide-field retinal images. Figure 7 illustrates the mosaics for two subjects from the FLoRI21 dataset. The mosaics successfully provide a continuous and extensive field-of-view of the retinal surface, despite that the evaluation results indicated less precise alignment. The effectiveness of our method is evident in the seamless transitions between overlapping images, only some image artifacts like halos or the date stamps are noticeable. However, some alignment errors can be observed, particularly in the mosaic on the right. These misalignments are noticeable in areas far from the reference image, where two target images overlap. In these regions we can observe some duplication of blood vessels even though the images are blended accurately. This demonstrates the robust performance of our method, which achieves visually cohesive mosaics even when alignment precision is not the highest. Finally, Figure 8 shows the resulting mosaics for two eyes from the LDRScreening dataset, with normalized images on the left and color images on the right. For the normalized images, the transitions between individual images are completely imperceptible, further highlighting the reliability of our α -blending approach. In the color images, overlaps are slightly visible due to variations in color intensities between the input images. Despite this, the alignment and blending of retinal structures, particularly the blood vessels, remains highly accurate. This result emphasizes both the precision of our registration method and the effectiveness of the blending approach, which together achieve seamless mosaics that faithfully represent the retinal surface.

These examples demonstrate the robustness and versatility of our method across different datasets, and different imaging modalities and conditions, establishing its value for creating wide-field mosaics in retinal imaging.

(a) Mosaic generated with normalized images

(b) Mosaic generated with color images

Figure 8: Examples of mosaics obtained for LDRScreening using the proposed α -blending method

7 Conclusions

In this work, we proposed a retinal image registration and mosaicking system that enables the creation of seamless wide-field views of the retinal surface. Our approach consists of a feature-based registration pipeline integrating advanced deep learning models for feature detection and description with a refined outlier rejection strategy. Outlier rejection consists of a two-stage RANSAC-based approach that captures both global and local deformations in each image pair, reducing the dominance of densely matched regions for obtaining a reliable and evenly distributed set of inliers. This is followed by an Approximate Thin-Plate Spline (ATPS) transformation, which offers a regularized and smoother version of the standard Thin-Plate Spline (TPS). The ATPS method mitigates the impact of potential mislocalized matches that may remain even after outlier rejection, ensuring a more accurate final transformation. Additionally, our α -blending technique ensures smooth and seamless mosaics, providing a comprehensive view of the retina.

The proposed system was extensively validated on multiple public datasets. First, we evaluated the impact of the techniques integrated into our retinal image registration method through an ablation study. Then, to assess its performance, we benchmarked our registration approach against state-of-the-art methods on the reference FIRE dataset. We also evaluated our method against leading deep learning approaches for feature matching. Furthermore, we validated the generalization capabilities of our method and the effectiveness of our mosaicking technique across different datasets.

Our method outperformed all previous state-of-the-art approaches across the entire FIRE dataset in retinal image registration, demonstrating its superior performance. Furthermore, we demonstrated that our system is both robust and versatile, achieving consistent performance across various datasets, imaging modalities, and conditions. Finally, our mosaicking method consistently generated seamless, high-quality mosaics, demonstrating the effectiveness of our approach in producing reliable wide-field retinal visualizations. Ultimately, the proposed system aims to enhance diagnostic accuracy and support more effective treatment planning in clinical practice.

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